

A N E M E L

Annual Report

Clean hydrogen
from dirty waters

2024

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About

ANEMEL

ANEMEL is a project, funded by the European Innovation Council and the Horizon Europe programme, focused on making green hydrogen from plentiful and sustainable resources, such as seawater and waste water.

To do this, the project will develop an electrolyser (a system that uses electricity to break water into hydrogen and oxygen) powered by green energy sources. This device will make use of non-critical raw materials within all its basic parts, including electrocatalysts and membranes.

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WP1 Catalysts

Catalysts make chemical reactions fast and efficient. At ANEMEL, we look for catalysts that accelerate water splitting – the process of breaking water into its two components, hydrogen and oxygen. More specifically, we need catalysts based on abundant metals like nickel, iron, and manganese. After WP1 developed these catalysts during the first year of our project, now we have worked on improving their properties, in collaboration with other WPs.

Electrolysers consist of two separate electrodes, the anode and the cathode. In the anode, catalysts oxidise water into oxygen gas, while the cathode drives the formation of hydrogen gas. Each of these redox reactions has different chemical requirements, which means each electrode requires different catalysts. And that is what this WP takes care of.

This year's work was a continuation from what began at the start of ANEMEL, with new developments primarily focused on the improvement of our catalysts. In the first 12 months of the project, our partners studied different nickel and iron salts, as these improve factors such as conductivity and electrode stability, in addition to being cheap and abundant metals. Our teams also worked on nickel-based catalysts, along with other compounds such as manganese oxide for the anode. They even explored bifunctional catalysts, which accelerate both hydrogen and oxygen production. Our main objective was to minimise the use of critical [raw materials](#) and prioritise simplicity by steering clear of complex coordination compounds, all with long-term sustainability in mind.

One of the biggest changes in this second year has been the addition of a new partner to the team, the [Jožef Stefan Institute in Ljubljana, Slovenia](#), thanks to the European Commission's "hop-on" facility for research institutions from Widening Countries. It has opened new possibilities

to explore a completely different family of materials that we hadn't studied before. This partner has worked with metallic boride nanoparticles. Prior to ANEMEL, they had already observed that the structure of boride enhances the tolerance to chloride ions, thanks to the formation of a "barrier". As a result, they have investigated which combinations of metals and boride offer the highest activity in alkaline systems, while also began to lower the pH and to incorporate chloride to assess their activity. They even have published part of their work in a paper, which recently appeared in the journal [Materials Today Energy](#).

ANEMEL also demonstrated the effectiveness of one of our catalysts in pure water, which was a major challenge for the project before progressing to seawater. We published this achievement in the journal [ACS Energy Letters](#). This was made possible through collaboration with other WPs, as some of the tests were conducted in fully assembled electrochemical cells.

Having access to these cells has been crucial for ANEMEL during the second year of the project. Although they are still far from becoming a complete, commercial electrolyser, they allow us to observe the performance of the different components when working together. Thanks to these cells, our researchers were able to run initial tests on our first year's catalysts, which were then optimised during the second year. This included adding some extra protection to ensure their stability in saline conditions.

Collaboration is key

Some of our catalysts were already good enough to be scaled up to a production of 2-3 grams, which is a significant amount for the current lab-scales. Once again, this wouldn't have been possible without collaboration with other working groups. Our partners from WP3 have provided the necessary tools to deposit the catalysts on the electrodes and to test their effectiveness. Because, in addition to the catalysts, we've also worked on identifying application methods onto the electrodes that we will use in saline conditions.

Our work doesn't just involve preparing the catalysts, but also depositing them onto the electrodes and testing them in the cells thanks to our collaboration with WP3." **(Pau Farràs)**

WP2 Membranes

Ions – electrically charged particles – travel through semipermeable membranes. We are developing these membranes using new compounds that will avoid the use of fluorine and fluorspar, both critical and contaminant raw materials. To achieve this, we work on composites based on functionalised polymers to ensure sufficient rigidity, in a collaborative environment that involves several ANEMEL partners. Our researchers have been able to overcome the obstacles encountered throughout the past year and achieve promising results.

[Membranes are essential for an electrolyser to work.](#) They keep the hydrogen and oxygen gases separated while allowing ions to pass through. However, making an efficient membrane is not that easy. Membranes are exposed to extremely reactive and corrosive conditions during electrolysis, particularly when using seawater, which is already a highly saline and highly oxidising environment.

That's why membranes have traditionally included fluorinated polymers, such as Teflon, to increase stability and durability. But stability is a double-edge sword, and (poly)fluorinated hydrocarbons have created conflicts related to recyclability and sustainability. At ANEMEL, we work to avoid these commonly called "forever chemicals", looking for stable polymers without fluorine.

We are pursuing a membrane that allows ions to move very quickly without losing their energy. Additionally, we want membranes to remain mechanically strong, to effectively separate the two sides of the electrolyser, while also being chemically stable, which in turn ensures a long lifespan. This contributes to the device's longevity, ultimately reducing the cost of hydrogen production.

To build our membranes, we work with polymers with different fluorine-free "functional groups", fragments that allow ions to move through the membrane quick enough, enhancing the efficiency of the electrolyser. That's key for conductivity. Here, cross-collaboration must consider the performance of the catalysts. For the catalysts to

function properly, we need to use a certain range of alkaline concentration, but these same alkaline conditions attack the functional groups of the membranes. During this year, we have worked on functional groups that can tolerate high alkaline levels, so that catalysis can work effectively while ensuring the membrane's durability. Among the achievements here, we have identified a novel head group, a positively charged functional group that allows negative hydroxide ions to move through the membrane, increasing stability.

Our membranes also require some form of scaffolding. As mentioned earlier, they need to remain mechanically strong to effectively separate the two sides of the electrolyser. But functionalising the membranes tends to soften them. During the first year, we observed that creating composites – by adding other materials to the membranes – helped achieve the necessary rigidity and stability. This year, we have designed fibres into which we can embed the functionalised polymers. While we may lose a bit of conductivity, we expect a significant improvement in the membrane's mechanical strength, ultimately extending its lifespan.

If anything characterised this WP during the second year of the project, compared to the first, it was the cooperative work among all its members. The partners involved in WP2 have exchanged samples between each other, combining their expertise to achieve the progress we've been discussing. This includes considering the scalability of the membranes. Scaling up some final products will be part of the next steps.

Co-polymers for our membranes

During the first year, our researchers drew inspiration from aromatic polymers, commonly used in fine protection due to their high temperature stability. However, these polymers didn't work as well as expected. So, for this second year, their focus has shifted to a co-polymer – a polymer made from two different types of units, in this case a combination of an aromatic and a linear monomer – called styrene-ethylene-butylene-styrene (SEBS). This co-polymer has some interesting features such as thermal stability, abrasion resistance and chemical resistance.

Our partners for scaling up provide us with tips at the lab level on what can also be implemented on a larger scale.”

(Mohamed Mamlouk)

WP3 Cells

Combining the electrocatalysts and membranes developed in other WPs, this team assembles complete electrolytic cells – the basic units for splitting water and generating green hydrogen. Cells have been a key focus this year in ANEMEL, as we successfully fabricated one that allowed us to test the catalysts from our partners in a more realistic way, accelerating our progress towards a functional electrolyser.

WP3 had a very busy year. This team is responsible for the electrolytic cells. That means assembling the electrodes, the electrolyte, the membrane, and eventually, an encasing system to hold everything together.

We previously mentioned in this report that we successfully accomplished the fabrication of a hardware cell, which was also sent from WP3 to other ANEMEL partners, primarily those in WP1. This means we now have a cross-platform setup throughout the project, allowing all partners to test their own catalysts more quickly.

While our goal is to understand the performance of the complete electrolyser, it's often helpful to identify weak points when the system is fully assembled. This specialised cell allows the insertion of additional reference electrodes, which provide a "window" to the different components of a membrane electrode assembly (MEA) – consisting of the anode, cathode, and membrane – separately.

The setup consists of a single-cell configuration. However, the hardware around it is essentially the same as that used

in a full stack, with an encasing system that holds every component, just on a different scale. For our project, a full stack consists of five cells working together.

Our partners also had some important deliverables and milestones to achieve over the past year. One of these was the fabrication of electrodes incorporating the catalysts from WP1, as we mentioned earlier. Although they successfully achieved it, the team still needs to test these electrodes.

The most challenging task, however, was testing how a full cell works in conjunction with our partners' catalysts. This milestone involved reaching a sufficient current density, essentially answering the question: how much current per volt can we generate under specific conditions? The specific goal was to achieve one amp per square centimetre at two volts at a temperature as low as 45°C. While we didn't strictly meet this at 45°C milestone, we did manage to stay within the range of 45-80°C. This was a crucial achievement for the project, opening the door to more ambitious goals moving forward.

Computational simulations to virtually test electrolysers' performance

Part of designing and developing electrolysers involves testing new materials. But tests take time. As a result, researchers sometimes rely on alternative solutions, such as computational simulations – programmes that model the electrolysis process to virtually explore different possibilities. This ensures that experimental efforts will focus on the most promising materials. This WP studied simulated MEAs to better understand the efficiency of water electrolysis. The findings were published in a peer-reviewed article in [Journal of Power Sources](#). Our researchers simulated a 1×1 cm² MEA based on commercially available materials, already proven viable. This allows us to calculate the performance of the electrolysers without moving into the fabrication phase, which provides a significant advantage.

Our cell allows us to decouple the contributions from the various elements, especially the catalysts, so we can assess their performance separately.”

(Fabio Dionigi)

WP4 Stacks

If a single cell is powerful, imagine a pile of them! We aim to build stacks of five cells, offering a more practical and scalable approach to hydrogen production. Our goal is to manufacture a stack robust enough to operate continuously, under stable conditions, for over 2,000 hours – that’s about three months! We’re still a bit away from reaching that target, but we’ve already made some significant progress during this year.

A stack is essentially a series of cells, five in the case of ANEMEL, assembled in a hardware setup. Thanks to this prototype we can test real-life features, which will facilitate the scale up towards industrial settings. But how are we connecting the cells? By using interconnects that ensure electrical contact while separating the gases produced – oxygen and hydrogen. This configuration allows us to sum the voltages of each cell while maintaining a consistent current throughout, thereby increasing the power output.

Our goal was to demonstrate a system with at least five cells producing one kilowatt of power, and we succeeded—even ahead of schedule! But there’s more. We aimed to achieve this without using platinum group metals (PGMs), which are highly resistant to corrosion but considered [critical raw materials](#).

This milestone is the result of extensive preparatory work. Our researchers have sourced the necessary materials, including large enough membranes – at least 10 by 10 cm – and big quantities of our catalytic materials. Additionally, they have produced the interconnects, which are specially

designed metal plates that facilitate water circulation and extract the generated hydrogen and oxygen. The design of these plates was carefully crafted to optimise the water flow and minimise the pressure drop, ensuring the system functions efficiently (and safely). This innovative flow field design is now in the process of being patented. another big success for us during this year!

We are currently working on selecting the best materials for each layer of the stack, focusing on options that resist corrosion under seawater conditions. This includes stainless steel coated with titanium nitride, nickel nitride, and other compounds. However, seawater corrosion has posed a significant challenge, delaying a bit our progress. So, this is also something under study right now.

Despite these challenges, we’re excited by the progress made. We even aimed for a five-kilowatt unit, and the test bench is already well underway. With some additional time, we expect it to be functional at atmospheric pressure by the end of the year.

Cells, stacks, electrolyzers... how does everything work together?

Electrolyser design allows for high modularity and scalability. The basic unit of an electrolyser, known as a 'cell,' consists of an anode, a cathode, and a membrane. In an electrolytic cell, electricity flows in through the cathode and returns to the circuit via the anode. These cells are then assembled into a 'cell stack' or simply a 'stack,' which increases hydrogen (and oxygen) production as more cells are added. When we apply an electrical current to the stack, we split water to form hydroxide ions (OH⁻), which move through the membrane towards the anode. The remaining hydrogen atom combines with electrons from the electrical current to produce hydrogen gas, while oxygen gas bubbles on the anode.

“ We achieved our milestone of developing a one-kilowatt power stack without the use of PGM materials well ahead of time.”
(Jan Van Herle)

WP5 Sustainability

We're committed to sustainability: from using green energy sources to implementing cleaner raw materials. WP5 ensures precisely that, pursuing an eco-friendly prototype design with minimal environmental impact. Our researchers will conduct a full life cycle analysis (LCA) and compare the results to industry standards, a task that has already started by collecting data from every partner to obtain preliminary assessments.

[Green is our favourite colour.](#) That means we take sustainability very seriously, making sure the design of our electrolyzers has the smallest possible environmental impact. Among other tasks, we will conduct a full life cycle analysis (LCA) and compare it to industry standards, ensuring our prototype is eco-friendly.

Throughout this year, our partners in charge of sustainability have met with each of the WPs and have begun collecting data from them, which they will model to obtain preliminary environmental impact assessments. To achieve this, they will use a specialised life cycle assessment software called openLCA.

Firstly, the data collected is primarily focused on the materials used, the energy consumed, and how waste is managed, to better understand the key aspects in the manufacture of electrolyzers. Parameters such as efficiency or component corrosion are also valuable in this context—essentially, factors that may affect the LCA and are relevant to electrolysis performance. Another important piece of data for calculating environmental impact is the information on the supply chain of the materials used—it's not the same to use a very abundant and accessible material rather than a one that's [difficult to extract and even scarce](#). This comes from a background database that is already eco-invented, not from our researchers.

When conducting an LCA, we also need a reference unit—much like metres for measuring distance or kelvin for temperature. Based on existing literature, our specialists have decided to use the functional unit of one kilogram of hydrogen produced over the lifetime of a one-kilowatt stack. This is, so to speak, our pilot unit. If we assume that this electrolyser will eventually scale up to industrial levels, we may need to consider a unit with more power capacity. However, the composition in terms of mass or weight of each component in a one-kilowatt electrolyser may not be proportional to a bigger one. Thus, the expertise of all our partners remains vital in this regard.

This team has also developed an Excel-based eco-design tool. The idea behind this tool is to replicate what the LCA software does but in a more accessible format. This allows all our partners to assess the environmental impacts of their products, even without a deep expertise in sustainability assessment. They can also adjust parameters that might influence that impact, helping to identify key areas for improvement to make our electrolyzers as green as possible.

As the participation of the entire consortium is crucial, future plans include a workshop with all partners to discuss how we can further improve ANEMEL technology in terms of sustainability. By that time, we will also expect to have a model of the ANEMEL technology from the LCA perspective, which will serve as a key starting point for analysing our work from an environmental standpoint. This workshop will also be an opportunity to introduce the eco-design tool.

Life-cycle assessment (LCA) to achieve more sustainable products.

Life-cycle assessment (LCA) is a comprehensive analytical method for evaluating the effects that a product, process, or service has on the environment. It is not limited to its manufacture or use but addresses the entire life span of the product. This includes all stages, from raw material extraction to distribution, use, and end-of-life disposal or recycling. However, this powerful tool goes beyond simply evaluating environmental impacts; it also explores options for reducing them by identifying opportunities for improvement across the entire life cycle of the element under assessment.

“In LCA collecting data is a task that can last for a long time. We succeeded to get some data from each partner during this year, so we are very happy with that.”
(Eleonora Crenna)

WP6 Communication

We not only do science, but we also explain it. Our main goal is to make the complex chemistry of ANEMEL understandable to everyone and ensure that the industry incorporates our innovative results into their product pipelines. Our impact should extend beyond the four years of European funding, thanks to clear, concise, and cutting-edge communication. This year, we have launched our webinar series, while keeping up with our blogposts writing and sharing our progress on social media.

Communicating and disseminating our project requires a well-thought-out plan. In the first year of ANEMEL, we delivered our promises: the establishment of a strong and coherent brand strategy to cement the project's presence. This involved creating a logo, a corporate colour palette, and a starter kit, which included an [infographic](#), an [animated video](#), and a [brochure](#). To this, we must add our different social media profiles on [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#) and a [website about the project](#).

With the foundations in place, this second year has been all about fully diving into communicating and disseminating our project. Through our social media channels and website, we have been sharing our latest developments, from publications to events, as well as celebrating our [successes](#). This has included introducing each of our partners in an ongoing initiative. We've also taken the opportunity to talk about the world of green hydrogen, writing more in-depth articles, such as one about [electrolysers](#) and another on [critical raw materials \(CRMs\)](#).

But the highlight of this year has undoubtedly been the launch of our ANEMEL webinar series, focusing on green hydrogen production, seawater electrolysis, and sustainability. For our inaugural session, held in February, we counted on the participation of Pau Farràs, our project coordinator and a researcher at the University of Galway, Ireland. We have also invited experts from outside ANEMEL to participate.

Our WP has also showcased the project at various events, including the 2024 edition of the European Innovation Council Summit, held in March during the Research and Innovation Week in Brussels. The goal of these communication and dissemination efforts is to engage with potential partners from both academia and industry while fostering strong connections with policymakers. Additionally, we have worked closely with other projects within our EIC Pathfinder challenge 'Novel Routes to Green Hydrogen Production.' In this context, we participated in the European Hydrogen Energy Conference (EHEC) in Bilbao, alongside our sister projects e-lobio and OHPERA.

Our new webinar series

In our very first webinar we could explore the opportunities in impure water electrolysis, a promising avenue for producing green hydrogen in a more sustainable way, thanks to our project coordinator Pau Farràs. He was followed by our researcher [Sahas Nuggehalli Sampathkumar](#) from EPFL, Switzerland. He helped us understand his [recently published paper](#) that studies [simulated membrane electrode assemblies \(MEA\)](#) to enhance the efficiency of water electrolysis. Lastly, [María Jaén](#), European Hydrogen Research Leader at EPRI Europe, explained the potential of hydrogen valleys for decarbonisation.

The communication and dissemination expertise is proving to be crucial in ensuring that the project results are widely valued by the scientific community.”

(Leyre Flamarique)

WP9

Portfolio activities

In ANEMEL, we're a team within a team. Because we belong to a wider group of projects under the European Innovation Council's (EIC) '[Novel routes to green hydrogen production](#)' Pathfinder challenge. This collaboration encompasses [nine consortia](#) with common objectives and similar research topics, with a combined funding of almost €29 million. [Green hydrogen](#) has a promising potential in the EU's strategy towards decarbonisation – the EIC portfolio of projects spearhead innovation in this field, creating cooperation mechanisms with other initiatives, such as the Clean Hydrogen Joint Undertaking, Hydrogen Valleys, and Hydrogen Europe, among others.

As part of the portfolio, we collaborate in actions related to communication, dissemination, and innovation – led by our partners the University of Galway, in Ireland, and Agata, in Spain. As part as this strategy, ANEMEL pioneered portfolio meetings, with the joint organisation of the 2023 general assembly in Tarragona, Spain, and the "[Hydrogen Horizons](#)" [event](#), which gathered over 100 experts from academia, start-ups, industry, and policymaking in ICIQ, a leading research centre in catalysis and clean fuels. Additionally, together with portfolio projects ELOBIO and OHPERA, we exhibited our latest results in a beautiful booth at the European Hydrogen Energy Conference (EHEC), which took place in Bilbao, Spain, between 6 and 8 March 2024. ANEMEL also participated in the 2024 general assembly of the portfolio of projects in Lyon, France, a few days ahead of the 18th International Congress on Catalysis.

Another key event towards the dissemination of portfolio results was "Harnessing renewables for a sustainable future", co-organised by the EIC in Genk, Belgium, and focused on green hydrogen and clean fuels for the circular economy. Our participation was strategic – bridging the gap between the 'Green Hydrogen' portfolio of projects and [other portfolios supported by similar funding mechanisms](#), including topics like carbon dioxide and nitrogen valorisation and Solar-to-X solutions. Moreover, this conference catalysed connections with academics (CNR, Cambridge

University, ESRF, Jülich), industrial leaders (Siemens, Toyota, Arcelor Mittal, Total Energies), policymakers (EIC, DG Climate, DG RTD) and maybe most importantly, investors and interested decisionmakers. ANEMEL also presented the portfolio results in international conferences, such as the 9th European Chemistry Congress in Dublin, Ireland, and the 268th American Chemical Society Meeting and Expo in Denver, United States.

The portfolio also fosters further innovation initiatives across projects, led by [Praveen Kumar Selvam](#) and Pau Farràs, from the University of Galway, Ireland. On top of attending EIC-organised programmes to promote cross-collaborations and foster technology transfer and entrepreneurship, this team has successfully secured funding from different sources to expand the interchange of ideas. Among other things, the [ANEMEL and ELOBIO projects partnered in a grant supported by the Irish Research Council](#) and the Embassy of France in Ireland.

Together, researchers will design and develop more efficient electrodes for electrocatalytic reactions, based on earth-abundant metals, such as nickel. The catalysts could find applications in seawater electrolysis – our holy grail in ANEMEL – as well as in the transformation of biomass into green hydrogen and value-added chemicals, the main milestone for ELOBIO.

Collaborations crystalise

This past year, ANEMEL presented the 'Green hydrogen' portfolio of projects in a myriad of conferences and events in Europe and the US. It's worth highlighting 'Hydrogen Horizons', co-organised by ANEMEL, and attended by over 100 experts in academia, start-ups, industry and policymaking. Moreover, we participated in the EIC Summit 2024, in Brussels, also attended by other portfolio projects and the 'Green Hydrogen' Programme Managers and Project Officers. During this event, our coordinator Pau Farràs pitched the project to an audience full of decisionmakers in policy and innovation, and joined the newest cohort of EIC Ambassadors. Several collaborations crystalised in 2024!

Collaboration across the 'Green Hydrogen' portfolio of projects is strategic: it saves resources but maximises exposure in key areas such as communication, dissemination and innovation”
(Fernando Gomollón Bel)

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